

a'gi fEG hqN uAsrsmS tolvpya&zDyHsm

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pmvrf t uDf

ppmvrf onf a'gi fEG hqN uAsrsm;wD haw&aom tolvpyf a&zDyHsm;uH
azm&w&ef &n&G fi avhvmwif yxm; ygon/ xD h avhvmwif y&mwD f tvsm;vHuf
tw&tpy! a'gi f vHuf tw&tpy! jrnob& tmar! dvi pojzih tofN trit&muHvHufi
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 aemulwGf v&phemusnt,zG &maumi faom b0\cpm;ruul yH ay:vG pth azmlus;EH fyg
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t o h t & n f t a o f w i t w i t p y i

t o h t & n f t a o f w i t w i t p y i n i w u f u s o h t w i t p y i f j z p o n i / j r e r m b m o m p u m ;
w i f o h v o ? o h w ? o h v ; [h o m w u f u s o h o h r s h & b n i / u A s m p m q u w l o n i o h v o ?
o h w ? o h v ; w i u i t a l u m i f t & m E s h m l u z u a t m i f t a v ; t a y g h t E k t u r f
a y : v o h a t m i f a & ; z h a v & u o n i /

] j y e f y g a v a w m h { n b o n q h } u A s m w o f a o ' e m q l b n h { n b o n l u m ; w i t g ; r a c g u l b l
r n b o n h t c s e f u O i f v m o n i u l r o d w i u r h r i y i f t 1 / 2 h t o m ; w i u i O g ; N r h c i f ; c h u u & o n i /
w i t g ; z o h E s f y g a o m i v n f a o r i f [b n h { n b o n q l u m ; a w ; q h r y s u y i f & h c s \ /
p m q l r h u l l g ; y g ; u h c h l r p h u s i b o h c h o m a l u m i h , c k t c g a o q h & e f t o i j z p a e n y d
j z p a l u m i f u l l -

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o d i f i v m ? i g r o d w i u f
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t 1 / 2 h t o m ; ? a o g a l u m r s m ; u h
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' P & m r j r i & ? c h u f v b d
c h e j r v u l t o n f c l u a t m i f
r u l r & u p u ? E h i v e f p h (a ' g i f E G h a q h 1996? 60)

[h o m t z d w o f t j c i f ? e m j c i f ? a o j c i f w n f [h o m a o ' e m w & m ; B u b o n i p m q l k b l
r z d w a c : b l O i h a & m u f v m a o m { n b o n q h u b o z g f y i j z p o n i / p t z d w o f o h v o f [l i
j y i ? O i } [h o m o h v o f r s m ; u l b m a w & h y d u s e h a o m a e & m r s m ; w i f o h w E s h o h v ; w i u i
t o h j y k x m ; & m t h e m ? a o j c i f w n f [h o m a o ' e m u h r E s h l o n h p m q l c h m ; r E s h
v l u z u b o n h t o l w e l q m q i r i [k q E h f y g o n i / p t z d w o f j a c g u l a y g u l v u l i u l
1 / 2 u l p l u l c l u l r l u l p o n h w i b o l u m & e f r s m ; ? a v ; a v ; y i f y i & G w i q & o n h] c ? b } p o n h
o h v i i (" e d w) (a s p i r a t e d) t u & m r s m ; y g i o a v o * P h j r m u h a o m t z d j z p o n i / t o j z p & m
a e & m (X m e) (p l a c e o f a r t i c u l a t i o n) c s i f w a o m t o h r s m ; o n i v n f t o h t & n i t a o f c s i f
w l y g o n i / p u m ; o j z p a y : o n h e & m w p c k w n f r s x u f v m a o m t o h r s m ; j z p i r t v e e d p y f
o n i / x b l X m e l w a o m t o h r s m ; u l e h e b u y u y i w b h a o m t z d r s m ; o n i v n f a & ; [e f
x l j c m ; r & b n i / (c i r i ? a r m i (" E j z l) ? 2010? 47 /)

o j z p i r t o h t & n f t a o f w i t w i t p y f t z d r s m ; o n i & G w i q & v g f u j c i f a l u m i h
t v g l w u l E l w i u f t m * h q m i E h j c i f ? t o h t & m a j y j p r i v n f & j c i f ? t a l u m i f t & m u l
a v ; e u b a y : v o h p j c i f ; p o n h t u s h t m e b i f u l j z p x e f a p o n i [k q E h f y g o n i /

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"A succession of sweetly melodious sounds. The term is applied to smoothly glowing Poetry or Prose" Kathleen Morner & Ralph Rausch, 1998, 71.